

LOW-CARBON HYDROGEN PRODUCTION POTENTIAL IN BRAZIL

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ABOUT EMP-LAC

The Energy Modelling Platform for Latin America and the Caribbean (EMP-LAC) is a noteworthy event organized through the OpTIMUS community. This free initiative offers participants access to proficient trainers, interactive discussion forums, and personalized coaching in using models and tools for energy planning and analysis. Notably, all the models and tools presented are both free and open source, emphasizing inclusivity and collaboration within the energy sector. Participants benefit not only from the event itself but also gain the flexibility to engage with courses at their own pace, thanks to the availability of resources on the OpenLearn platform. This holistic approach not only promotes knowledge exchange but also empowers individuals to enhance their skills in energy modelling, fostering a community dedicated to sustainable energy practices in the region.

For further information, please visit: <https://climatecompatiblegrowth.com/summer-school-and-teaching-materials/>

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Energy Access Explorer (EAE) was employed to estimate the potential for hydrogen (H₂) production, taking into consideration factors such as electric power generation potential, socio-environmental restrictions, and proximity to the National Interconnected System (SIN). Additionally, the analysis incorporated the generation of new energy to avoid disruptions to existing electricity demand in Brazil.

In the methodology for calculating solar and wind renewable energy potential, data from various sources, including Wind and Solar Atlases, IBAMA Conservation Units, Transmission Lines, Substations, and Urban Infrastructure, were collected and integrated into ArcGIS. Spatial analyses using the Solar and Wind Atlas layers identified areas with high potential for renewable energy generation, considering solar irradiation, wind speed, and topography. The assessment also factored in environmental restrictions from IBAMA Conservation Units and evaluated the proximity of identified areas to existing electrical infrastructure. Thematic maps representing solar and wind potential, environmental restrictions, and proximity to infrastructure were generated and exported to the Energy Access Explorer (EAE) for further analysis and integration.

The objective of this report is to estimate the potential for H₂ production from renewable sources using the Energy Access Explorer.

INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen has the potential to initiate a paradigm shift in the energy sector, bringing substantial opportunities for Latin America to emerge as a global leader, particularly in low-carbon hydrogen. This is considering the abundant and competitive renewable energy resources in the region, contributing significantly to the strong decarbonization of industries and the transportation sector.

The fact that Brazil is highly competitive in renewable energies and possesses extensive untapped potential serves as a strong foundation for the low-carbon hydrogen industry. Brazil also has natural gas and other significant energy resources, water resources, national uranium reserves, and nuclear technology. With a robust infrastructure, including logistics and ports, a solid and modern energy sector, as well as a skilled workforce, Brazil is well-positioned to develop its significant low-carbon hydrogen market potential and export to the world, leveraging its distance from major developed markets (EPE, 2021).

Hydrogen has become a priority in the energy and climate strategy of many countries, primarily providing an alternative for sectors with challenging carbon emission reductions (hard-to-abate sectors) and serving as an energy vector, enabling energy storage and facilitating the coupling of the energy sector with the industrial and transportation sectors (IEA, 2019). Even in light transport, hydrogen can play a significant role, offering another technological alternative for the electrification of vehicles (directly through fuel cells or indirectly through synthetic fuels – e-fuels).

METHODOLOGY

Methodology for Calculating Solar and Wind Renewable Energy Potential Using ArcGIS Layers and Exporting to the Energy Access Explorer (EAE):

1. Data Collection:

Gather necessary data, including information from the Wind and Solar Atlases, IBAMA Conservation Units, Transmission Lines, Substations, and Urban Infrastructure.

2. Data Integration in ArcGIS:

Import layers into the ArcGIS software, ensuring correct integration and overlay of information

3. Solar and Wind Potential Analysis:

Using the Solar and Wind Atlas layers to perform spatial analyses and identify areas with high potential for solar and wind energy generation.

Consider factors such as solar irradiation, wind speed, and topography to assess the potential for energy production.

4. Identification of Environmental Restrictions:

Analyze IBAMA Conservation Units to identify protected areas and establish restrictions or guidelines for renewable energy project development.

5. Infrastructure Analysis:

Use Transmission Lines and Substations layers to assess the proximity of identified areas to existing electrical infrastructure.

Identify areas where connection to the electrical grid is viable and cost-effective.

6. Urban Infrastructure Assessment:

Consider urban infrastructure to evaluate potential restrictions or opportunities associated with the development of renewable energy projects in urban areas.

7. Results Mapping:

Generate thematic maps representing solar and wind potential, environmental restrictions, and proximity to electrical and urban infrastructure.

The objective of this report is to estimate the potential for H2 production from renewable sources using the Energy Access Explorer.

8. Export to Energy Access Explorer (EAE):

Export consolidated results to EAE, ensuring compatibility and effective integration with the platform.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using this methodology, the potential for green hydrogen that would meet the additionality criteria, addressing the electrical demand and low-carbon hydrogen production by subtracting final demands from resource inventory values, is 21 Gtep. The estimate of the available energy resource balance for hydrogen production on an annual basis is as follows:

Figure 1 - Wind resources

Source: EPE, 2024

Figure 2 - Solar resources

Source: EPE, 2024

Figure 3 - Brazilian National Grid

Figure 4 - Conservation Units

Source: EPE, 2024

CONCLUSION

Hydrogen, though not a new source, is gaining momentum as a low-carbon energy solution, presenting challenges yet offering diverse business opportunities across various industries such as oil and gas, renewables, biofuels, nuclear, and more. Its competitive cost makes it applicable in diverse economic activities like transportation, energy generation, storage, fertilizers, steel

production, refining, and bio-refining, including the production of advanced biofuels. The global hydrogen market, particularly driven by green, blue, and turquoise hydrogen, is expanding. In the electric sector, the impact is expected on both electricity demand for electrolyzers and the expansion of renewable energy sources, influencing transmission network growth. Brazil, with its abundant and low-cost renewable energy, is well-positioned for hydrogen production, not only as a supplier of green commodities but also as a competitive hydrogen economy exporting minerals, steel, metals, ammonia, agricultural commodities, and other low or zero-carbon industrial goods and services. Employing GIS tools is fundamental for these types of studies, and utilizing the EAE platform can be particularly beneficial for area calculation, accounting for socio-environmental constraints. Additionally, it allows us to visualize site opportunities with optimal competitiveness concerning the available energy resources for this study.

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